

Condensation of Ethyl Acetoacetate with Aromatic Amines. Part I.

BY G. V. JADHAV.

Ethyl acetoacetate gives different condensation products with aromatic amines, according to the conditions of reaction. Knorr (*Ber.*, 1883, 16, 2598) at first regarded the product obtained from aniline and acetoacetic ester to be $\text{Me}\cdot\text{C}(\text{NHPh})=\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$, but later on (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 542) he changed his views and assigned the constitution, $\text{Me}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NHPh}$. He worked with aniline, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-toluidines, naphthylamines and *o*-phenylenediamine.

Later on Conard and Limpach (*Ber.*, 1883, 21, 521) carried out the condensation of the same and some other amines at room temperature with the methyl ester and found that the products obtained were the derivatives of crotonic acid, namely $\text{Me}\cdot\text{C}(\text{NHR})=\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}_2\text{Me}$. The same workers also condensed the ethyl ester with *p*-anisidine and got a similar product (*Ber.*, 1888, 21, 1651). Later on Ewing and King extended the work of Knorr to prepare new dimethyltetrahydroquinolines (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 113, 106).

No attempt seems to have been made to see the effect of substituents in the nucleus on the course of the reaction. The present work was undertaken to prepare some substituted quinoline derivatives, which would be described later on.

o-, *m*-, and *p*-Nitroanilines, *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-chloroanilines, *p*-anisidine, *p*-phenetidine and *m*-xylydines (1:4:5 and 1:3:4) were employed. Of these *o*-nitroaniline did not condense even after prolonged boiling with ethyl acetoacetate. The condensation products of the other amines could be divided into three classes:

- (i) $\text{Me}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NHR}$
- (ii) $\text{Me}\cdot\text{C}(\text{NHR}):\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$
- and (iii) $\text{Me}\cdot\text{C}(\text{NHR}):\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NHR}$.

The substances of the type (iii) are decomposed by hydrochloric acid giving substances of the type (i), in the case of *m*- and *p*-

nitroanilines, while the compounds obtained from other amines are perfectly stable even towards boiling hydrochloric acid.

The compounds of the type (ii) are obtained in the case of *p*-nitroaniline, *p*-chloroaniline and *p*-phenetidine. In the last two cases the reaction takes place at room temperature. Anilides of type (i) are obtained in the case of *m*-nitroaniline, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloroanilines and *p*-anisidine. Xylidines give products of the type (iii). It should be noted however that products of the type (iii) together with varying proportions of other products either of the type (i) or (iii) are obtained in all cases, if the reaction mixture is heated for a longer time. The substances of the type (i) and (ii) do not give any colouration with ferric chloride, but those of the type (i) give violet to blue colour as expected.

The latter react with ammonia giving aminocrotonanilides as obtained by Knorr (*Ber.*, 1892, 25, 775). In the case of *p*-anisidine, *p*-phenetidine and the chloroanilines, water separates out from the reaction mixture as soon as they are mixed with ethyl acetate but the isolation of the product at this stage is found possible only in two cases, *viz.*, *p*-phenetidine and *p*-chloroaniline. If the same mixture is heated, the product is an anilide (type i). It therefore seems that an ester of the aminocrotonic acid is first formed and the water liberated in the reaction then hydrolyses the aminoester and the more stable amide is formed.

The formation of compounds of the type (iii) together with those of type (i) and (ii) can be explained as follows:—

A little of the latter that are formed reacts with free amines forming some of the type (iii). Thus there is always an equilibrium between the two.

That the reaction takes the above course in the formation of compounds of type (iii) is supported by the fact that the anilide (type i) or anilincrotonic ester (type ii) when heated with an aniline gives a compound of the type (iii).

The stability of the compounds depends upon the basicity of the anilines used as is suggested by Fierz-David and Ziegler (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1928, 11, 776). This is also proved by the fact that the diamides (type iii) of nitroanilines (which are less basic) are hydrolysed by hydrochloric acid in the cold into anilines and mono-anilides (i). While similar compounds of chloroanilines, methoxy-, and ethoxy-anilines and xylidines are perfectly stable towards the same acid even when boiled with it.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Acetoacet-m-nitroanilide.—Ethyl acetoacetate (10 g.) was mixed with *m*-nitroaniline (10 g.) when heat was absorbed. The mixture was then refluxed with an air condenser for about four hours. The red liquid was then allowed to cool. On cooling some solid was obtained. It was then heated on a water-bath for about three hours to remove the alcohol formed in the reaction. The solid obtained was then triturated with ether to remove the adhering ester and unacted amine and washed with it. The residue crystallised as pale yellow needles from boiling water, m. p. 120-21°. It is soluble in most organic solvents like alcohol, chloroform, acetic acid and difficultly soluble in ether and benzene. (Found: N, 12·80. $C_{10}H_{10}O_4N_2$ requires N, 12·61 per cent.). A deep yellow solid insoluble in water was also obtained.

β -m-Nitroanilinocroton-m-nitroanilide.—The ester (10 g.) and the amine (15 g.) were mixed and heated as before for about ten hours. After the removal of alcohol, the product was washed as before with ether. The mono-amide formed is removed by repeated boiling with water. The yellow insoluble portion is then crystallised from a large quantity of benzene, m. p. 152-153°. The same compound is obtained if the mononilide obtained in the previous experiment is heated at 140-150° for about four hours with *m*-nitroaniline. (Found: N, 16·40. $C_{16}H_{14}O_5N_4$ requires N, 16·38 per cent.).

Action of Hydrochloric Acid on β -m-Nitroanilinocroton-m-nitroanilide.—The substance (1 g.) was treated with cold hydrochloric acid (3 c.c.). The yellow solid began to change colour and became white. After about one hour, it was filtered and washed with water till free from acid. The insoluble substance was then crystallised from boiling water in pale yellow needles, m. p. 119-120°. Mixed melting point with acetoacet-*m*-nitroanilide described before is also 119-120°.

Action of Ammonia on Acetoacet-m-nitroanilide: Formation of β -Amidocroton-m-nitroanilide.—The anilide (1 g.) and concentrated ammonia in excess were boiled for 15-20 minutes, more ammonia being added at intervals. The orange coloured turbid solution gave orange-red needles on cooling. These were washed with cold water till free from ammonia, and were found to be soluble in alcohol and benzene, m. p. 129-130°. (Found: N, 18·74. $C_{10}H_{11}O_3N_3$ requires N, 19·00 per cent.).

Ethyl β-p-Nitroanilincrotonate.—Ethyl acetoacetate (10 g.) and *p*-nitroaniline (10 g.) were mixed and boiled under a reflux condenser for about five hours. The alcohol was removed from the mixture by heating on a water-bath for about an hour. On cooling an orange solid was obtained. It was then triturated and washed with benzene when the orange coloured solid remained behind and the benzene solution on evaporation gave a yellow solid. The latter crystallised from alcohol in needles, m. p. 122-123°. (Found: N, 11.46. $C_{12}H_{14}N_2O_4$ requires N, 11.20 per cent.).

β-p-Nitroanilincroton-p-nitroanilide.—The orange coloured solid insoluble in benzene in the previous experiment was extracted with boiling water to remove the unacted *p*-nitroaniline. The orange solid insoluble in water was found to be insoluble in most organic solvents. It was crystallised from boiling nitrobenzene in orange needles, m. p. above 250°.

If the compound of m. p. 122-123° obtained in the previous experiment is heated with *p*-nitroaniline at 160-170° for five hours it gives the same compound. (Found: N, 16.03. $C_{16}H_{14}O_5N_4$ requires N, 16.38 per cent.).

Action of Hydrochloric Acid on β-p-Nitroanilincroton-p-nitroanilide: Formation of Acetoacet-p-nitroanilide.—The compound (1 g.) was treated with cold hydrochloric acid (5 g.). The orange solid began to change colour at once and became yellow. It was left in contact with the acid for about half an hour with occasional stirring. It was then filtered and washed free from acid. The insoluble mass was crystallised from alcohol in needles, m. p. 122-123°. Mixed melting point with ethyl *β-p*-nitroanilincrotonate was 100-105°. This anilide when heated with *p*-nitroaniline at 140-150° gives the dianilide described before. This seems to be identical with that described by Fierz-David and Ziegler (*loc. cit.*) who gives its m. p. 119°. (Found: N, 12.89. $C_{10}H_{10}O_4N_2$ requires N, 12.61 per cent.).

β-Aminocroton-p-nitroanilide.—The anilide (1 g.) was heated with strong ammonia for about 15 minutes with occasional addition of fresh ammonia. On cooling, yellow needles were obtained. These were collected and washed free from ammonia, m. p. 189-190°. (Found: N, 18.73. $C_{10}H_{11}O_3N_3$ requires N, 19.0 per cent.).

Acetoacet-p-anisidide.—*p*-Anisidine (10 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (10 g.) were heated under a reflux condenser in an oil-bath at 130-140° for about eight hours. The dark greenish mixture was allowed to cool when a solid separated out, which was washed with

ether to remove some adhering oil. It was soluble in most organic solvents, and crystallised from boiling water in irregular plates, m. p. 117-118°. (Found: N, 7.08. $C_{11}H_{13}O_3N$ requires N, 6.76 per cent.).

β-Aminocroton-p-anisidide.—The anisidide (1 g.) was mixed with strong ammonia when it went into solution which was shaken for three hours and then left overnight. Next day when ammonia was evaporated off at room temperature, a solid separated. This was then filtered, washed free from ammonia and crystallised from ether in needles, m. p. 109-110°. (Found: N, 13.34. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires N, 13.58 per cent.).

β-p-Anisidino-p-anisidide—Ethyl acetoacetate (10 g.) and *p*-anisidine (10 g.) were boiled under reflux for about an hour; when the red liquid was allowed to cool, it gave some solid. It was then diluted with alcohol and washed with it. The solid was then crystallised from glacial acetic acid in needles, m. p. 235-236°. This same compound is obtained by heating acetoacet-*p*-anisidide with *p*-anisidine at 160-170° for about 5 hours. (Found: N, 9.21. $C_{15}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires N, 8.97 per cent.).

Ethyl p-Phenetidinocrotonate.—Ethyl acetoacetate (10 g.) and *p*-phenetidine (10 g.) were mixed. When the mixture began to get turbid due to the separation of water, it was put in a desiccator. After two days, a crystalline solid separated out. As it was found to be easily soluble in common organic solvents, the solid was allowed to dry on a porous plate for some days. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in irregular plates m. p. 60-61°. (Found: N, 6.04. $C_{14}H_{19}O_3N$ requires N, 5.62 per cent.).

β-p-Phenetidinocroton-p-phenetidide.—Ethyl acetoacetate (10 g.) and *p*-phenetidine (10 g.) were boiled under a reflux condenser for about 45 minutes. When signs of solid formation were visible, the hot mixture was allowed to cool. It was then triturated and washed with ether to remove the adhering oil. The solid was crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m. p. 230-231°.

This substance was also obtained by heating ethyl *β-p*-phenetidino-crotonate with *p*-phenetidine at 160-170° for 5 hours. (Found: N, 8.41. $C_{20}H_{24}O_3N_2$ requires N, 8.24 per cent.).

β-m-(1:4:5)-Xylidinocroton-m-(1:4:5)-xylidide.—Xylidine (12 g.) and the ester (18 g.) were mixed together and rapidly boiled under reflux for about one hour. On cooling a solid separated out which

was triturated with alcohol to remove the adhering oily impurities. It was practically insoluble in alcohol, benzene, toluene, ether, chloroform or acetone. It crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m. p. above 275°. (Found: N, 9.88. $C_{20}H_{24}ON_2$ requires N, 9.09 per cent.).

β -m-(1:3:4)-Xylidinocroton-m-(1:3:4)-xylidide.—The reaction was carried out as in the preceding case, the heating being continued for about two hours. It is insoluble in most organic solvents. It crystallised from glacial acetic acid in needles, m. p. above 275°. (Found: N, 9.16. $C_{20}H_{24}ON_2$ requires N, 9.09 per cent.).

Acetoacet-m-chloroanilide.—Ethyl acetoacetate (10 g.) and *m*-chloroaniline (10 g.) were boiled under reflux for about one hour. The brown liquid was heated on a water-bath to remove alcohol. On cooling the liquid gave a crystalline solid. It was then triturated and washed with ether to remove the excess of the ester and the amine. The solid was found easily soluble in most common organic solvents but difficultly in boiling water. It crystallised from dilute acetic acid in irregular plates, m. p. 105-106°. (Found: Cl, 16.68; N, 6.97. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2NCl$ requires Cl, 16.78; 6.62 N, per cent.).

β -m-Chloroanilinocroton-m-chloroanilide.—Ethyl acetoacetate (5 g.) and *m*-chloroaniline (7 g.) were boiled with an air condenser for two hours and the red liquid was then allowed to cool. The pasty mass was washed with ether and the solid crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 240-241°. The same substance was obtained by heating acetoacet-*m*-chloroanilide with *m*-chloroaniline at 160-170° for about 4 hours. (Found: Cl, 22.30; N, 8.59. $C_{16}H_{14}ON_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 22.12; N, 8.72 per cent.).

Acetoacet-p-chloroanilide.—The ester (10 g.) and the amine (10 g.) were mixed and boiled with a reflux condenser for about two hours. The mixture was then allowed to cool when a solid separated out. It was then washed with ether to remove the unacted ester and amine, when a white crystalline substance was obtained, which crystallised from boiling water, m.p. 132-133°. (Found: Cl, 16.67; N, 7.08. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2NCl$ requires Cl, 16.78; N, 6.62 per cent.).

β -Aminocroton-p-chloroanilide.—Acetoacet-*p*-chloroanilide (1 g.) was mixed with liquor ammonia, when the solid went into solution; the solution was shaken for about six hours. Much solid separated out from the solution which was filtered off and washed free from ammonia. The mother-liquor gave more solid as ammonia evaporated, m. p.

110°. (Found: N, 12·95; Cl, 16·72. $C_{10}H_{11}ON_2Cl$ requires N, 13·30; Cl, 16·87 per cent.).

Ethyl β -p-Chloroanilinoacronate.—Ethyl acetoacetate (15 g.) and *p*-chloroaniline (15 g.) were mixed in a beaker. When the solution began to be turbid due to the separation of water, it was kept in a desiccator. After three days a crystalline solid separated out. As it was very soluble in most organic solvents, it was dried on a porous plate. The solid was finally crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 55°. (Found: Cl, 14·48; N, 6·07. $C_{12}H_{14}O_2NCl$ requires Cl, 14·82; N, 5·85 per cent.).

β -p-Chloroanilinoacron-p-chloroanilide.—Ethyl acetoacetate (5 g.) and *p*-chloroaniline (10 g.) were boiled with a reflux condenser for about two hours. A solid separated, when the heating was stopped. It was washed with benzene, when colourless needles were obtained, m.p. above 275°. The same substance was obtained by heating acetoacet-*p*-chloroanilide or ethyl β -*p*-chloroanilinoacronate with *p*-chloroaniline at 140-150° for five hours. (Found: Cl, 22·48; N, 8·82. $C_{16}H_{14}ON_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 22·12; N, 8·72 per cent.).

Acetoacet-o-chloroanilide.—The ester (10 g.) and *o*-chloroaniline (10 g.) were mixed and refluxed with an air condenser for about twenty minutes. The yellowish liquid was then heated on a water-bath to remove the alcohol formed in the reaction. On allowing the reddish liquid to cool, crystals were obtained which when filtered and washed with ether became white. These crystallised from very dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 107-108°. This is the same as described by Fierz-David and Ziegler (*loc. cit.*). It is easily soluble in alcohol, chloroform, benzene, acetone and glacial acetic acid. (Found: Cl, 16·46; N, 6·91. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2NCl$ requires N, 6·62; Cl, 16·78 per cent.).

A small solid residue insoluble in alcoholic water was left behind which was crystallised from alcohol; m.p. 286°.

β -Aminocroton-o-chloroanilide.—Some of the anilide obtained in the previous experiment was mixed with liquor ammonia, when the solid went into solution. The solution was shaken for six hours and left overnight. It was again shaken next day for six hours more. Some solid separated out which was filtered and washed free from ammonia. The solution left on evaporation of the ammonia at room temperature gave more solid, m. p. 96-97°. (Found: N, 13·54; Cl, 16·98. $C_{10}H_{11}ON_2Cl$ requires N, 13·30; Cl, 16·87 per cent.).

β-o-Chloroanilinocroton-o-chloroanilide.—The ester (10 g.) and aniline (15 g.) were mixed and refluxed with an air condenser for about an hour and a half. The red liquid was allowed to cool when a solid separated out. The mixture was triturated and washed with ether to remove the adhering oily impurity. The white solid thus obtained was insoluble in water and was crystallised from boiling alcohol. By mixed m.p. it was identified with the solid obtained in the previous experiment in a very small quantity. Its m. p. was 236°. The same compound is obtained by heating acetoacet-*o*-chloroanilide with *o*-chloroaniline at 140-150° for about five hours. (Found: Cl, 21·85; N, 9·12. $C_{18}H_{14}ON_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 22·12; N, 8·72 per cent.).

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,

THE ROYAL INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE, BOMBAY.

Received March 17, 1930.